

Peopling in the Empire's Borderland: A Note on Kuki History and Ancestry in Northeast India

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This paper examines the history and ancestry of the Tibeto-Burman Family (TBF) in general and the “Kuki-Chin Group” of the TBF in particular. It argues against the dominant colonial civilizational narrative that ridiculed the whole tribal peoples in Northeast India as “peoples without history”. Based on the written accounts (both religious and secular) of the valley states and societies surrounding their mountain redoubts, supplemented by objective linguistic, genetic, and archaeological sources, studies in recent years have successfully reconstructed the history of the tribes since the ancient period. The latest genetic studies show that the ancestry of TBF in the region dates back to the second millennium BCE. Studies on ancient literature show that Kukis are the “Tilabharas” of Mahabharata, the “Tiladai” of Ptolemy’s *Geography*, and the “Thalutae” of Pliny’s *History*. Buddhist sources knew them as “Ko-ki” which had become, in the Bengal world since ancient times, the generic nomenclature for the hills tribes of the southern Himalayas. One copper-plate inscription from ancient Tripura (Bengal) is a testament to the “Kuki” ancestry on the eastern frontier of Bengal. Their presence in the rolling mountains between Bengal and Burma plains in the medieval world is also testified by the *Rajmala* and *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the royal chronicles of Tripura and Manipur respectively, the Burmese inscriptions, and the Tang Chinese chronicle. Their megalithic remains, which are of a living tradition amongst them until recent times, are a living testimony of their ancestry in the southern Himalayas.

Keywords: Northeast India, Burma, Tripura, Manipur, Mizoram, Chin Hills, Kuki, Zo, Mizo, Chin, History, Ancestry

Introduction

The tribal people of Northeast India have been often ridiculed as “peoples without history” just because they “lacked” some tangible historical sources such as written historical accounts and archaeological sources. Suspecting the authenticity of oral histories, and by using an equally bias account of the colonial civilizational discourses,

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their history had started from the colonial period. Critics of colonial writings, some recent studies, however, pointed out the biased accounts of the tribes as to pushing back their histories to the ancient period. Archaeological and genetic studies particularly prove promising in this respect. The latest genetic studies show that the ancestry of TBF in the region could date back to the second millennium BCE which some archaeological findings have supplemented. We will come back to these studies shortly in the case of the Kukis.

In a geographical space such as India's northeastern highland, which is predominantly inhabited by one socio-cultural group, the "Tibeto-Burman Family" (TBF), it is certainly a messy intellectual exercise to examine the history of one particular group within the larger TBF. To see them even at the largest social compass at hand, say, Kuki, Naga, Meitei, Garo, Bodo, Karbi, and so on, could still produce tension is certain. The problem lies not only in the way the colonial state attempted to straighten, in the interest of rule, the multiple, porous, and pliable social formation process with its crazy-quilt patterns of tribal classificatory order but also in how tribal people have appropriated such patterns as given as the basis of ethnic assertion and political contestation. The colonial fissures and fragments have therefore become an intellectual tool to understand the past of the tribes.

This paper examines the case of the Kuki or "Kuki-Chin Group" of the TBF who are known today by a constellation of names – Kuki, Chin, Mizo, Zomi, Hmar, Komrem, Khulmi, Hallam, etc. It attempts to bring together the existing studies on Kukis and organize them within the context of some objective historical accounts. It argues that Kukis are one of the ancient tribes of eastern India which have constant contact with valley-based civilizations surrounding their mountain redoubt. Earlier studies show that Kukis were the "Tilabharas" of Mahabharata, the "Tiladai" of Ptolemy's *Geography*, and the "Thalutae" of Pliny's *History*. Ancient inscriptions of Tripura (Bengal) recorded them as "Kuki" and noted their presence in eastern Bengal as paddy cultivators. *Rajmala* and *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the royal chronicles of Tripura and Manipur respectively, provided detailed accounts of the Kukis in medieval eastern India. They were also known to the medieval Burmese inscriptions and chronicles as well as the Tang Chinese chronicle. Above all, the widespread megalithic remains of their past, which are of a living tradition until recent times amongst them, are living testimony of their ancestry in the southern Himalayas, between Bengal and Burma plains.

The name "Kuki"

The term "Kuki" is used here in the context of Manipur but it is chosen mainly for being perhaps the oldest name given to the linguistic "Kuki-Chin Group" by any civilization. There was no such known common nomenclature of the distant past but they generally uttered "Zô" or "Zhô" (highland or highlander) when speaking to others (the valley people). The term "Zô" resembles a widely prevalent phonological term across the Zomia (highland region of China, Southeast Asia, and Northeast India), such as Hiou, Shou, Sho, Dzo, Yaw, Jô, Hao, Jhumia, etc. From a Chinese civilizational narrative, also shared by Manipur and Burma, the terms refer to uncivilized and uncouth tribes of the rolling mountains.

A recent study by Indrani Chatterjee noted that the term “Ko-ki” was originally conceived in Buddhist usage, which means, the “birth of incarnate Buddhas” or “incarnated Buddhas” (meaning, followers of Buddhism). (Chatterjee, 2013: 2). It originally refers to Buddhist converts of what Taranatha (1608) has called the “Ko-ki countries”, a vast swath of territory along the coast, from the eastern frontier of Bengal up to Southeast Asian mainland. Taranatha suggested that the name “Ko-ki” was conceived during the time of Emperor Asoka Maurya who had “*samghas*” established in the “Ko-ki countries”. (Taranatha, 1608: 330). Since then, “Ko-ki” or “Kuki” has become the generic name for the hill tribes of the eastern frontier of Bengal. The Panchakhanda Copper-plate inscription of ancient Tripura, dated 641 CE, identified “Kuki” as a settled agriculturist population in eastern Bengal. (Bhattacharjee, 2017: 13-19).¹

In their classification of tribes, the British borrowed the name “Kuki” from the Bengalis which they later found to be “accidentally correct” or accurate, ethnologically. Yet, in their earnestness for the rule, the name was later trifurcated into Kuki, Chin (in Chin Hills), and Lushai (Lushai Hills). They are presently known by a constellation of names; the name Kuki being adopted by a small section of the population as their generic nomenclature. The pertinent point is that this group of TBF is the only remaining group who are still struggling for a common name despite accepting the fact that they belong to “one and the same stock”. (Carey & Tuck, 1896-I: 2).

This paper is not interested in pushing through “Kuki” amidst the colonial and postcolonial fissures and fragments. It is merely interested in adopting the name (“Kuki”) adopted by Indian civilization for historical and intellectual consistency and clarity. Otherwise, the Kukis knew themselves by the name “Zô” or “Zhô” (highland, in their language), probably another civilizational term as noted earlier. Way back in 1798, for instance, Francis Buchanan recorded them calling themselves as “Zou”:

They name their own tribe Zou. By the Ma-ra-mas they are named Lang-ga, which by the Bengalese is corrupted into Lingta. By the Bengalese they are commonly called Koongky [Kuki], which we have corrupted into Kooky, or as it is written in the Asiatic Researches Cuci. (van Schendel, 1992: 94)

J.G. Scott (1900: 452) also similarly noted:

In their northern extension, these tribes are collectively known as Kuki. The term Lushai, which is applied farther south, is not recognized by the people themselves, who use the name Zhô. Shendu is also a synonymous title for the Lushai tribes. In the country between Bengal and Burma, the tribes are known as Khyin [Chins] in the east and by a variety of local names in Bengal.

Kuki belongs to TBF: Linguistic and Ethnographic Studies

Although language has been considered to be one of the most dynamic and fragile instruments, it has become, since the colonial period, the most reliable source for reconstructing the affinities of different tribes and families. Significant contributions have been made since then. It was generally agreed that “Tibeto-Burman Family” (TBF) belonged to the same mongoloid stock and that their original home or the

“cradle” and “geographical centre of gravity” is in northeast Tibet (identifiable as Sichuan and possibly Yunnan region of China). (van Driem, 2001). It was from this region that they marched down toward the tropics and colonized a vast swath of territory until the sea.

Linguistic and ethnographic studies also agreed in general that the Kukis belong to the TBF. The *Linguistic Survey of India* (1903) put them together under the “Kuki-Chin Group” of the TBF, which also includes the Meiteis of the valley of Manipur. G.A. Grierson (1903: III) claimed that he had merely followed Damant’s classification. G.H. Damant (1880: 230) claimed that the “classification of the Kuki family is probably more correct” than what he does to other groups. This classification was accepted without any demeanor by the successive studies on the Kuki-Chin group. E.W. Dun (1886: 32), for instance, wrote:

In other cases where a large number of tribes have been classed together (Abors, Singphos, Nagas), the difference between tribes separated socially and geographically from one another has, since the imposition of the name, been discovered to be so great as to suggest doubts as to the advisability of attempting any such wide generic classification; but in the case of the Kukis, all the tribes (with indeed the exception of the Pois) have so many common grounds of affinity, that the classification seems to have been, however *accidental, correct*. [*Emphasis mine*]

From their ethnological point of view, studies done by a range of British officers such as John Edgar, W. McCulloch, T.H. Lewin, R. Brown, B.S. Carey, J. Shakespear, W. Shaw, etc., “Kukis” belonged to “one and the same stock”. B.S. Carey and H.N. Tuck (I, 1896: 16), for instance, noted:

...the Kukis of Manipur, the Lushais of Bengal and Assam, and the Chins originally lived in what we now know as Thibet, and are of *one and the same stock*; their form of government, method of cultivation, manners and customs, beliefs and traditions *all point to one origin*. (see also, Shaw, 1928: 16). [*Emphasis mine*.]

John Shakespear, who studied all the tribes belonging to the Kuki, remarked: “Nevertheless there is no doubt that the Kukis, Chins, and Lushais are all of the same race”. (Shakespear, 1912: 8). He called it “Kuki race”, who knew themselves by the name “Mi-Zo”. (Ibid.).

The linguistic and ethnographic studies, however, could not provide the precise date of the arrival of Tibeto-Burman speaking people in the Northeast Indian highland. The geographical location of the different “Groups” of TBF in the region merely suggests that the “Kuki-Chin Group” was at the bridgehead of the long march toward the tropics (the Bay of Bengal). However, this should not necessarily imply that they were the first group in a series of migrations and colonization of the region. Recent genetic studies show that the TBF arrived in the region together, in groups, and then spread out in different directions.

Kukis in Eastern India: Genetic Studies

One of the major findings of recent genetic studies is that the original home of the

Tibeto-Burman speaking people in the region is, consistent with linguistic evidence, East Asia (China) with whom they shared their genetic ancestry. In the course of time, they also developed a distinct genetic trait from East Asian ancestry known as the Southern Tibeto-Burman (STB). On the one hand, the Y-Chromosomes of STB “consistently show strikingly high homogeneity among groups and strong affinities to East Asian group”. On the other, there was a striking “genetic discontinuity between northeast Indian groups and other Indian groups”. The greatly reduced Y-Chromosomes are best explained by a “male founder effect” whose arrival and colonization of Northeast India is estimated to be somewhere about 4000 years ago (i.e. around the second millennium BCE). (see, Cordaux, et. al., 2003; Cordaux, et. al., 2004; Wen, et. al., 2004; Gayden, et. al., 2009).

The homogeneity in the genetic inheritance among the Indian Trans-Himalyan STB ancestry in the region vis-à-vis the Indian subcontinent and East/Southeast Asia suggests two objective historical circumstances. That, the Northeast Indian highland massif was a geographical barrier, rather than a corridor, of human migrations in history between the Indian subcontinent and East/Southeast Asia. That, this Trans-Himalyan STB ancestry had arrived together in the Northeast region at one point in time rather than in a wave of immigration. In other words, the ancestry of the Tibeto-Burman family in Northeast India was attributed to a group of closely related male founders rather than waves of immigrants from East Asia.

DNA studies on the Mizo (one of the Kuki-Chin linguistic group) also similarly show that they share the East Asian specific ancestry but also belong to the same stock of other Indian Trans-Himalyan STB ancestry who shared a distinct trait from East Asian ancestry. (Bankura, et. al., 2024). Being part of the STB, the “Kuki-Chin Group” of the TBF also arrived in the region along with other groups. Their geographical location, which is at the advance guard of southward migration, merely suggests them as being more adventurous and audacious than the other groups. Their legend of migration also suggested that they migrated toward the south and retraced their footprints when they reached “a large expanse of water” (Bay of Bengal?). (Shaw, 1928: 28-30).

An important takeaway from genetic studies is that the STB groups arrived in the region “together” in about the second millennium BCE and spread out in different directions. It is yet to be ascertained why they had to migrate towards the tropics but Herold Wiens’ argument that the expansion of the Han Chinese state and civilization toward the south, amongst the Non-Han Chinese people, led to the migration of the latter population toward the south, could hold true in the case of this ancient migration as well. (Wiens, 1954; Scott, 2009). With the advancement of genetic studies, especially on the ongoing ancient DNA studies, it is hoped that the dating question should also be eventually resolved in due course.

Kukis in Eastern India: Ancient Literatures

Like many other tribes of the region, the Kukis also had a legend of the “lost script”, written on a parchment (*savunjol*). Legend apart, they were generally known as people without scripts and writing. They largely depended on orality, memory, symbols, and

performances to transmit their history and culture. Yet, their mountain redoubts have been fortunate to have been encircled by some valley-based civilizations – east, west, and north – who wrote about them. Despite being scanty, obscured, and usually prejudiced, such written accounts constituted indispensable sources to reconstruct their past.

G.R. Gerini's *Researches on Ptolemy's Geography* (1909) pointed out that the "Kukis" of the Northeast region (who called themselves "Zhô") are the "Tiladai" of Ptolemy's *Geography* and the "Thalutae" of Pliny's *History*. Tiladai is identified by scholars as the "Tilabharas" of the Mahabharata. (Gerini, 1909: 53, 744) This would mean that the Kukis were one of the ancient tribes of eastern India.

Gerini's account is supplemented by Buddhist literature. Taranatha's *History of Buddhism in India* (1608) referred to the name "Ko-ki" as a place and people in ancient eastern India. In Chapter 39, he discusses in length the "account of the spread of the [Buddhist] doctrine in the Ko-ki country in the east". To him, the eastern world was divided into three parts – Aparantaka, Girivarta (Kamarupa, Tripura, Hasama), and Ko-ki (which includes "countries" along the sea, extending from the eastern frontier of Bengal to mainland Southeast Asia). He wrote: "From the time of Asoka [3rd Century BCE], *samgha-s* were established in these Ko-ki countries. Later on, these gradually grew large in number" (Taranatha, 1608: 330).

Although the translator confused "Ko-ki" with the Chinese word *tszyaochzhi*, a recent study shows that the term "Ko-ki" was derived from Tibetan Buddhist usage for those Buddhist converts in the lands they called "Ko-ki countries". Indrani Chatterjee noted that "Kuki" is originally derived from the Tibetan Buddhist usage of "Ko-ki", meaning, the "birth of incarnate Buddhas" or "incarnated Buddhas", meaning followers of Buddha. (Chatterjee, 2013: 2). It was from this original tongue in Buddhist vocabulary that the term "Kuki" came to be used in the Bengal world, since ancient times, as the generic nomenclature for the hill tribes inhabiting the eastern mountains of Bengal. Buddhist literature also suggested that some of the Kuki population could have adopted Buddhism as their religion, a fact that still needs to be established.

The term "Kuki" seems to have been initially religious throughout the eastern highland and has been testified by the Meitei (Manipuri) old manuscripts, *Puyas*. To the ancient Meiteis, "Kuki" means a pious mendicant, probably the Buddhist mendicants/missionaries who might have traveled across the region. The term was understood as "Lai" (religious person or god). Thus, a phrase like "*Kooki Ahongba, Laiki Achouba*" (good god of peace) was usually uttered while praying.

The royal chronicle of Tripura, *Sri Rajmala* clearly established that a good number of the Kuki population had been a great devotee of Lord Shiva. *Rajmala* also used Kuki and Kirata synonymously as belonging to one tribe, testifying to the fact that they might have been "the lost" (I prefer to use, the "remaining") tribe (Kirata) of the Mahabharatas. The Tripura chronicle was not shying away from recording the popular stories circulated in the Tripura kingdom that narrate the close association of Lord Siva with his Kuki devotees, particularly Kuki women folks.

One very popular story was that during the reign of "Kumar, the fifty-seventh in succession", who visited Sam Alanagar, "the dwelling place of Siva, who at the time fell violently in love with a Kuki [woman]". On hearing this, Siva's wife (goddess

Parvati) got angry and “kicked the [Kuki] woman so violently to break her neck”. (Long, 1850: 539). N.C. Nath’s translation of *Sri Rajmala* narrates:

In the Kirata land, there was a city called Chambala (King Kumara) a great devotee of S’iva, had gone to that land, when the fortunate king found a shrine of Mahadeva called Subadaikhung, and paid his homage there. (The story goes that) Lord Mahadeva had kept a Kuki woman there, whom Parvati found out later on, and catching her by the hair, trampled her throat under foot. As a result, the Kuki woman had her throat split in two. Since then, the Kuki women have a low voice. This story is widely circulated in Tripura (Nath, 1999: 44).

Rajmala went on narrating “another curious story” current in the city of Chambala “that S’iva had assumed the Linga form by himself in that place. By night S’iva had amorous sports with the Kuki women, and by day his body was mistaken as a stone and was thrown away by the people”. (Ibid.).

During the reign of Sri Dhanya Manikya, the king received a report of the dealings of Lord Siva (Siva Linga) with the Kuki women (Kukini) in “Kuki land”. The son-in-law of the king, Hopa Kalau was “deputed to the Kuki land to bring the S’iva-linga from there”. The son-in-law went there, seized the said Siva Linga from Kuki’s possession, put it into a betel case (*panbata*) with care, wrapped it over in cloth, set a seal on the packet, and sent it to the king in “great haste”. When it was presented before the king, it was found that the Siva Linga “had already escaped from the case somewhere on the way”. It was learned that the Linga was there in the betel-case up to the other bank of the river Manu. But when the bearer was crossing that river, “the Linga returned from there to its original site” in the “Kuki land”. On hearing this, the king, wailing, said to himself, “the lotus-feet (of Siva) that even Brahma is unable to touch, I, the lowest of the low, want to catch hold of”. (ibid.: 90).

The Kukis had a high veneration for Lord Siva is also evident from the fact that Bhuban caves, which lie at the heart of the then “Kuki lands”, have become the sacred seat of the deity in the subsequent period.² John Shakespear (1912) referred to one Kuki legend of how they had first discovered and began worshipping the “images in the Bhuban caves” which came to be known as the Linga of Lord Siva. The legend says:

Long ago Zatea stole a mithan belonging to two Biate chiefs, Chonlut and Manlal, and on their trying to recover their property they were severely wounded. On their way home they noticed that the leaves of the “bung” [banyan] tree, a species of *Ficus*, attached themselves to their clothes, and at night they dreamt the leaves saying, “Do not throw us away; we are sent by the gods of the Bhuban caves to heal you”. They applied the leaves to their wounds and were soon healed, and then set off in search of these new gods. (Shakespear, 1912: 187).

The main cave is still considered by the Kukis as one of the gateways to *mithikho*, the subterranean world/village of the dead people.³

The Burmese chronicles also understood the Kuki people as “Khyan/Kyang” (corrupted as Chins by the British) and “Jò/Yaw”. Gordon Luce noted that the Burmese called the Chin people “Khyan” or “Kyang”. (Luce, 1985: 77). Fr. Sangermano (1893) noted that the Burmese chronicle described the hill people living to the west of Kale-

Kabaw valley and on the Chin Hills as “Jò (Yaw)” or “Chien” (Chin). (Sangermano, 1833: 43). The Tang Chinese chronicle of the 9th century, *Manshu*, referred to the Chin people as “Mi-no” or “Shou” and the Tangs knew the Chindwin River as “Mino-chiang” (Luce, 1961: 90).

Kukis in Eastern India: Archaeological Evidences

The Kukis have been already well-settled agriculturists in eastern India since ancient times is evident from the copper-plate inscription of ancient Tripura. The *Panchakhanda Copper-plate* of Tripura (641 CE) mentioned a land grant offered by the Tripura king Srisrijukta Adidharmapha to “five saintly Brahmins” from Mithila whose land was:

...bounded on north and west by the curved Kroshirâ (Kosiyârâ) river and on the south and east by the settlements of the Hânkulâ Kukis, within which paddy was cultivated by the Tengkori Kukis on this fifteenth day of the brighter half of the month of Makara (Pausa/mid-December to mid-January), 51 Tripurâbda (i.e. 641 CE). (Bhattacharjee, 2017: 13-19).

The *Itâ Copper-plate* (1194 CE) inscription of Tripura also corroborated the continuous settlement of the Kukis in Tripura in the medieval period. It relates to another land grant offered by Srisrijukta Svadharmapha to the saintly Mithila Brahmins. The land granted to them was over (as the inscription read):

...the Kuki inhabited land in Manukula Pradesha bounded by Langlâ hill on the east; forest of Chandra Singha Tripura and river Manu on the south; river Gopala on the west; and river Kosiyara on the north, on this thirteenth day of the brighter half of the month of Megha (Asada/mid-June to mid-July) in 604 Tripurabda (i.e. 1194 CE). (Bhattacharjee, 2017: 136).⁴

The fact that the Kukis had inhabited the rolling mountain ranges between Bengal and Burma plains since ancient times is also evident from the remains of Burmese inscriptions. The Kukis were known in Burmese chronicle as “Khyan” or “Kyang”, corrupted and standardized by the British as “Chin”. The Burmese inscriptions of 1272 and 1299 CE referred to the present-day Chindwin River as “Khyan-twan”, literally, the “Hole of the Chins” (Luce, 1985: 77).

Kukis in Eastern India: Megalithic Traditions

The widespread megalithic culture, which was still practiced as a living tradition among the Kuki/Zo peoples in recent times, is another testimony of their ancestry in the region. Local historians (mostly based on oral histories) tend to reconstruct the history of Mizoram based on the dominant clan (Thangura and particularly the Sailo clan) there and undermine the presence of large numbers of other clans. Worst, based on such family histories, some of them concluded that the Mizo people arrived in Mizoram in the eighteenth century (Pudaite, 1963; Lalhangliana, 1977; Vumson, 1986; etc.).⁵ Reconstruction of the history of a community or a place based on the histories of just one family or clan is not only unscientific in a situation where clans and families were constantly shifting from place to place for political or economic or health reasons. It is

also not supported by the histories of other families/clans.

Thangura was estimated to be born in the eighteenth century and his children and great-grandchildren were able to rule over the whole Lushai hills by the nineteenth century is a fact. (Shakespeare, 1912: 3-6) It is also a fact that they ruled over all the other families and clans who have been there in the hills since time immemorial. It should be noted that successive academic interventions on the history of the Mizo people have already shown the fact that they have always been there in Mizoram since the ancient past.

We have already shown in the previous paragraphs how the northern part of Mizoram was once nominally under the Tripura kingdom as part of its Purvakul or “Kuki lands”. The Mizo peoples who lived there were known in Rajmala as “Kuki” whose ancestry in the region could be traced back to prehistoric or ancient times as is evident from ancient inscriptions, Buddhist and Hindu texts, and so on. They are the authors of the widespread megalithic remains across the rolling mountains between the Bengal and Burma plains that mapped and testified their ancestry in the land.

Recent research on the megalithic traditions in the Chin Hills (by Francois Robinne), Mizoram (by Malsawmliana and Lalhminghlua & Amrita Sarkar), and southern hills of Manipur (by D.L. Haokip) shows that the megalithic tradition found there was not only unique and widespread across the mountain ranges but shows that they represent the core cultural collective of the Kuki/Mizo peoples who had continued the tradition until very recent times. (Malsawmliana, 2017; Robinne, 2015; Lalhminghlua & Sarkar 2017; Haokip, 2021).

An archaeological excavation under the Archaeological Survey of India in 2015-2016 at the Vangchhia megalithic site in Mizoram shows a flourishing megalithic civilization over the mountains for centuries. Carbon dating of the material remains shows the cultural sequence in two periods – circa 600 CE to 1400 CE and circa 1400 CE to 1750 CE. The unique water pavilions found at the site belong to the first period. The menhirs, burial sites, and the potsherds belong to the second. (Das, 2018).

While the dating of other older sites is yet to reveal different dates, this dating may be taken as the benchmark period for the widespread megalithic culture of the Kuki/Zo people in the southern Himalayas. If the so-called “water pavilions” (which some archaeologists suspected of post-holes or otherwise) represent the high noon of their civilization in the land, their ancestry in the land may be pushed back to prehistoric times. The promising ancient DNA study is likely to take us to a further conclusion.

The Kuki megalithicism came in two traditions; the older tradition, without any engravings, and the later tradition with elaborate engraving motifs. While the older traditions are still to be seen in different parts of their land, what had become dominant are the engraved menhirs. The latter comes with unique features, such as the stones largely of stela type (upright stone slab or column), standing in different sizes, erected near the village by the roadside (mountain trails), and covered with elaborately engraved motifs (petroglyphs) of extremely intricate designs. Sometimes they are also engraved on the natural rocky surfaces.

The motifs consisted of humans, animals, birds, weapons, ornaments, and certain unknown designs related to their worldview/cosmology (see, Fig. 1-4). The whole design of the engraved megaliths informs not only an outstanding artistic, historical,

and anthropological significance but also the material wealth of the village or the person who had erected the monument.

The erection of megaliths is part of their important rituals and ceremonies related to their warrior traditions. The most common occasion is the “feasts of merit” (variously known as *Chon*, *Ton*, *Khaungchawi*, *Thangchhuah* feast, etc.). Such stones were also erected during *Sa-ai* (ceremony of big games) and *Bu-ai* (ceremony of bumper harvest/ rice) and certain festivals like the *Sikpui Ruoi* of Hmars or *Thajinglap* of the Vaipheis. The stones are popularly known as *muolsuong* (stone on the mount) as they are normally erected on the mount near the village, along the mountain trail. The rituals associated with the erection of such stones are variously known as *suongphu*, *suongdo*, *lungphum*, *lungkam*, etc. (stone erection ceremony).

Fig. 1. Specimens of older tradition found across the region (Photo by Author)

Malsawmliana explains that the structures are primarily “commemorative in nature”, describing the importance of fertility cult, social merit and continuity, and eschatological beliefs, among others. (Malsawmliana, 2017). Robinne argued that the scenes depicted “military exploits, sacrificial rituals, and shamanic voyages”. (Robinne, 2015). Haokip traced the artistic representations of the cumulative lifestyle from prehistoric times to a much later period where interpolation is not ruled out. (Haokip, 2021). Whether the stela represents also of the phallic architecture is not clear. They are therefore commemorative and sacred, related to social merit and continuity, the economic wealth of the society, eschatological beliefs, and possibly a fertility cult. They mapped the ancestry and ancestral territory of the Kuki/Zo peoples in the highland region.

Fig. 2. Specimen from Vangchhia (menhirs in left picture bears similar motifs as in the right) (Photo by Author)

Fig. 3. Specimens from Chin Hills and Manipur (Photo by Robinne and Author)

Fig. 4. Recent tradition: Petroglyphs (with roman scripts) at old sites of Khaokol (1935), Teiseng (1971), Buhsau (n.d), and Zenhang Bazaar (1979) (Photo by Author)

Kukis in Eastern India: Evidence from Tripura chronicle, *Rajmala*

Perhaps the greatest detail of Kuki history in medieval India is provided by the royal chronicle of the kingdom of Tripura, *Sri Rajmala*. The extent of the medieval Tripura kingdom includes, besides the present Tripura and parts of the eastern Bengal plain, the whole of Cachar plain (Barak valley) and its surrounding mountain ranges toward the east (south-western hills of present Manipur up to the foothills of Thangjing range in Moirang) and the south (northern ranges of present Mizoram). Its eastern border was said to extend, at one point in time, up to the valley of Burma. The hilly part of its eastern frontier territory (up to the valley of Manipur), the northern part of Mizoram, the lower ranges of Cachar (Hedamba) plain, were known in *Rajmala* as “*Purvaku!*” or “Kuki lands” and the people who inhabited this land were known as “Kukis”. The chronicle used “Kuki” and “Kerat” or “Kirata” often synonymously.

Rajmala mentions the expansion of the Tripura kingdom across the mountain ranges toward the east and south of the Cachar plain (Hedamba). This expansion brought many of the Kuki chieftains of the mountains under its tributary network. It mentions that the Kukis of the east were brought under Tripura rule as tributary chiefs through “conciliation” whereas the southern Kukis were subjugated by “armed clashes”. (Nath, 1999: 81). This process went on until the late medieval period, leading to the expansion of Tripura’s eastern boundary up to the valley of Manipur. The dominions of Tripura are even said: “to have stretched nearly as far as Amarpur in Burmah” (Long, 1850: 540).

Of the important battles against the Kuki chieftains of the south, the one that led to the conquest of the Thanangchi (Thanansi) mountain fortress, during the reign of King Dhanya Manikya (1490-1515), remains a legend in the Tripura chronicle.⁶ It took over more than a year of seize and conquest of the fortress. The reason for its conquest was, *Rajmala* noted, due to the refusal of the Kuki chief of Thanangchi fort to give up his priceless possession, the white elephant, and that this mountain chieftain “robs the [other] Kukis by force if they try to come to this path (of sub-mission to Tripura)”. (Nath, 1999: 79-80).

Rajmala mentions that the conquest of Thanangchi hills brought large numbers of Kuki chieftains from the east under the Tripura tributary networks. It mentions that as the army General Raykacag stationed himself at Sambul, he sent “emissaries” to Kuki chieftains, and as a result, tribes like “Chaka Rankhal, Khama Rankhal, Gunaircha, Kharchung, Marchil, and Kuki – all beginning from the eastern frontier (*purvaku!*) met Raykacag with the rich present, as was the custom all along”. The General then “recounted their past and present history” and said to them, “You are all along the faithful subjects of Tripura”. He convinced them that they felt astray from the “rightful path” and asked them to “offer presents to the king and the Fourteen gods”. The Kukis then accordingly swore before their deity – “We will not take our food without first making presents to the king”. (Ibid.: 81).

The General then sent the Kukis to the king with their presents which include “elephants’ tusks, yaks, goats, gong-bells made of peuter spacious and colourful fabrics of red, black and white hue, peuter plates, and jugs, spittoons (*pikdani*), copper bangles (*Kankan*), water vessels called Ubapheru, Cedar (*Deodar*) wood,

Kirata swords, and spear”.

Thousands of Kukis, all stark naked, came to the king taking with them various things and horses of different colour. The king was highly pleased to see their presents. (Ibid.: 81)

The king was very happy also to the General for his achievement and since then treated him “like his son”, *Rajmala* remarked.

Rajmala also mentions some of the major contributions of the Kukis in Tripura state formation from its inception. This came, not only in terms of the wealth they contributed to the kingdom but also as a source of manpower for the soldiers and commanders of Tripura army, fighting all its wars and diplomacy. Of the wealth they contributed, *Rajmala* mentions the various tributes and presents in the forms of precious metals and other exotic items. For instance, when king Trilochan (the 47th king) conquered the Hedamba (Cachar) and performed the “ceremonies for the fourteen gods”, it was the Kukis and the Kerats who contributed all the animals for sacrificial purposes and helped the priests in performing the sacrifice.

On their arrival [with the Deodai priests] they performed the usual ceremonies to the fourteen gods, with offerings of buffaloes and ducks for sacrifice which were collected by the Kerats and Kukis. (Long, 1850: 538).

A large amount of gifts were also brought down by the Kukis when Trilochan was born: Presentations of horses and elephants were pouring in day by day. The Kiratas [to mean Kukis] paid their annual revenue along with presentations. They brought gold, silver, copper, clothes, yaks and goats of the Kuki hills with abnormal horns and beautiful white fleece (fur) and beard. They also brought valuable “aguru” wood (agallochum) and gong bells made of brass, iron and bell-metal (kamsya) (Nath, 1999: 26).

Besides their usual presents to the king, *Rajmala* also mentions, for instance, the war booties from the Thanangchi hills, brought by the General to the king.

The king was sitting on the throne when the General made his appearance with the gifts. King Dhanya Manikya was highly pleased to see the profuse gold, silver and drapery (presented by him)... The king smiled and showed great honour to him. He sent him home with gifts of clothes, flowers and an elephant. Raykacag also had a large number of villages like a prince (ibid.: 82).

When Kalyan Manikya (1626) became the king, “the high-lander Kuki subjects arrived with horses, yaks and clothes. They also brought dishes, gong bells (ghong), elephant tusks, and other presents for the king. They gave these presents to the king, and received cloths and ornaments as their rewards (*inam*)”. (Ibid.: 175).

The Kukis also served the kingdom as army commanders, foot soldiers, and irregular forces. For instance, when the land of Rangamati was conquered, *Rajmala* recorded that it was the “Kuki soldiers” who moved at the head of Tripura army. (Ibid.: 50). After the annexation of Khandal, king Dhanya Manikya, instructed a Kuki chieftain (Sardar) to count the soldiers of Tripura army.

The king sat on an elevated platform there and asked a Kuki Chieftain (Sardar) to count the soldiers present there. The soldiers were engaged in cooking and eating in a merry mood. The chieftain went before them to do the counting. He performed the counting by touching the ranks with a wooden cooking stick (*anna yasthi*) of the army. Those who were touched while eating came to be known as *kathi-choya* (stick-touched). Those who came forward before the touch and ate afterward were regarded the best; those who had food in their mouth at the time of touching were regarded the lowest... Thus, large numbers of soldiers came to be reckoned as *kathi-choya* (touched with a wooden stick) from the days of Dhanya Manikya. (Ibid.: 77).

Kukis in Eastern India: Evidence from Manipur chronicle, Cheitharol Kumbaba

Cheitharol Kumbaba, the court chronicle of Manipur kings, provided (mostly in brief) the war and diplomacy of Manipur rulers with the hill tribes surrounding the valley and beyond. Historically, Manipur's attention was drawn by the rulers of the east (Burma) and most of its trade and diplomacy were also directed toward the east. The occasional invasions of Tripura (Takhel/Takhen) into the valley since the seventeenth century also drew its attention toward the west (Bengal). Within its wars and diplomacy with Tripura, one also began to notice the account of the Kukis who lived under Tripura's suzerainty. However, *Cheitharol* was silent on the southern mountains until about the 1790s when Manipur sent its first military expedition against the Saiton (Seitol) hills. This section examines Manipur's relationship with the Kuki tribes of the southern Himalayas in general and the Kukis of the southern mountains surrounding the valley of Manipur.

Cheitharol initially recorded the Kuki tribes by different tribal names or their village names. However, since the eighteenth century the name "Khongjai" or "Khongchai" was gradually adopted as the generic name for the whole Kuki tribes. It was originally derived from one of the famous Kuki villages called "Khongsai" on the Kailam-Senting ranges of the southwestern mountains. In 1734, Manipur was able to end the suzerain power of the Tripura kingdom over its Purvakul or "Kuki lands" (the southwestern hills of present Manipur), inhabited by the Kuki tribes. This led to the rise of some Kuki chiefdoms on its ruins which were, however, slowly decimated or restrained by the Manipur kingdom.

Khongsai (Khongjai) chiefdom, one of the rising Kuki chiefdoms, was destroyed by Manipur army in 1786. Manipur's military expeditions toward the southern mountains in 1790, and then peaked after 1826, restrained the rise of other Kuki chiefdoms. Through war and diplomacy, Manipur was able to bring in a large number of Kuki chieftains into friendly relationships. Due to such a relationship, their hills were eventually brought under Manipur administration by the British Boundary Commission in 1894. Manipur's relationship with the Kuki tribes is examined in the following paragraphs under three sections, based on their geographical and historical relationship with Manipur, as recorded in the *Cheitharol*. Oral traditions are invoked whenever necessary.

Manipur and the Kukis of Kale-Kabaw Valley

Of the Kuki groups, which Manipur had an early political dealing was perhaps the Chins/Kukis of Kale-Kabaw valley in Burma. *Cheitharol* occasionally recorded people/

place called “Kyang”. We have noted that “Kyang” or “Khyen” (corrupted as “Chin” by the British) is the name given by the Shans and Burmese of Upper Burma to the Kuki tribes who lived on their western mountain (Yoma) ranges and part of the Kale-Kabaw valleys.

The Lushei and Khyeng (Asho) tribes of the Chin Hills still talk about their “Fort of Khampat”. The Khyeng (Asho) still preserves one time-tested ballad that talks about “the brick (walled) city of our forefathers” that is “not a little charming”. (Fryer, 1875: 46-47). The Lushei tradition talked about the history of their kingdom centered at Khampat which was destroyed by the Shans. Before leaving the place, a banyan tree was planted there which still stands today. The prophecy, the millennial belief, was that when the branch of that banyan tree touches the ground and is rooted, they will return to the place to rebuild their kingdom. (Lalthingiana, 1977: 87-91).

The Lushei’s legend possibly referred to the destruction of Khampat by the combined forces of the Pong and Manipur kingdoms in 1467/1474. *Cheitharol* mentions the defeat of Kyangs or “Kyang Khampat of Kapo” (Raja of Khumbat in Pong/Shan Chronicle) in 1467 by the Manipur king Meetingu Kyampa with the help of Choupha Khekkhompa, the king of Pong. (Parratt, I, 2005: 38-39). The Pong Chronicle (1474) referred to a “strong fort” of the Rajah of Khumbat which was besieged and the Raja escaped “on a spotted elephant”. (Pemberton, 1835: 113). It was possible that since after this defeat, Khampat was occupied by the Pong’s tributary, the Shan Sabwas which Manipur had dealt with in subsequent periods while continuing to describe the territory as “the land of Kyang”.⁷ Kyangs continued to appear intermittently in the *Cheitharol* till the eighteenth century but largely concerning the territory of Khampat.

Manipur and the Kukis of Southern Mountains

The fact that Manipur had no political or commercial interest in the southern mountains until the nineteenth century was largely responsible for the splendid silence of *Cheitharol*. R.B. Pemberton, the first British official explorer in the region, in the early nineteenth century, was unable to extract any definite geographical information, let alone the ethnographical information, of the southern mountains from the people of the Manipur valley. The only information he could gather was the myth of “Imphal Toorel falls” known to them as “Chingdunhoot [Chingnunghut], or Mountain Penetrator”. This led Pemberton to assume that “there must either be a rapid succession of falls... or one or two stupendous magnitudes”. Pemberton (1835: 24) remarked:

...it is in this unexplored portion of its course, that *a fall is said to exist*, over which the stream is precipitated with *fearful velocity*; this spot is known to the Muneepoores by the name Chingdunhoot, or Mountain Penetrator; but I have never been able to discover an inhabitant of the country who had personally examined it.

Pemberton went on to describe that the ignorance was due mainly to “a well-founded apprehension of the tribes, who occupy the ranges between which the river flows” which had “hitherto prevented any examination of so remote a spot”. (Ibid.: 24). The southern mountains were therefore always a distinct geographical entity to Manipur since the dim past. Their knowledge was shrouded with mysteries. The mysterious

mountains were known in *Cheitharol* as the abode of a mythical bird called *Kakyen* which had “overpowered men” and “carrying men off” so that “no one was able to move about” (Parratt, I: 23).

During the reign of Taothingmang in Kangla, with his brother, they carried out an expedition up to the southern corner of the valley called Lokkha Haokha (a village said to be Sugnu or nearby it) where people live in constant fear of the *Kakyen*. The two brothers set up a trap, caught the *Kakyen*, and killed it. With one of its wings, they sealed the entrance of a cave (also known as *Chingnunghut*, the mountain penetrator), and with another, they dammed up the waters of Loktak river, so a lake was eventually formed. The people of Lokkha Haokha became so scared of them that they “lived in fear and trembling”. (Ibid.: 23).

S.N.A. Parratt, the translator of *Cheitharol*, understood *Kakyen* as *Khakyen*, a Shan state in Upper Burma. There was no such state called *Khakyen* unless one referred to the *Khyang* of *Khampat* referred to earlier. The uncanny phonological resemblance of *Kakyen* and *Khyen* or *Khyang* (Chin) is however deceptive. As noted earlier, the term *Khyen* or *Khyang* is identified as Chin lead one to assume that *Kakyen* here would mean the tribal people of the southern mountains. This is evident from the very use of the term like *Lokkha* (southern river) and *Haokha* (southern tribes). The fact that *Kakyen* troubled the people of the southern valley informs a constant fear of raids from the hill tribes.

Pemberton’s view that the apprehension of the hill tribes prevented the valley populace from knowing anything about the mountains and its inhabitants holds true. Indeed, the world of *Kakyen* only registers the cultural worldview of a dark, dangerous and wild country inhabited by “barbaric” tribes, typical of valley-based civilizational narrative. The absence of any definite geographical and ethnological information about the southern mountains, beyond the *Chingnunghut*, in *Cheitharol* or otherwise is therefore not a surprise.

It should not however be taken to believe that *Cheitharol* was completely unaware of the southern mountains. The Anal (Anan or Namphou) tribe, who inhabited the lower ranges of the south-eastern hills, with its principal village at Anal Khullen, were well-known in the *Cheitharol* for a long time. As the Moirang kingdom was taken, and contact with the southern tribes increased in the eighteenth century, *Cheitharol* also came to develop an idea that the tribal people of the south-east and southern mountains (*Khaki hao*) belonged to the same Kuki tribes of what they called *Khongjai/Khongchai* of the south-western hills.

Cheitharol had initially recorded them as “*Khaki/gi Haos*” or “*Haos of Khaki/gi*” (southern tribes) or sometimes by the name of their principal villages like “*Chasat Haos*” (Chassad Haokip villages on the Haosapi [Haobi] range), “*Saiton Haos*” (Seitol Haokip villages of the Thangjing/ting ranges), “*Lomyang Haos*” (Lamyang Guite villages of the “*Guite Kual*”), the “*Sumtan Haos*”, the *Yangpi* [Changpi] hao, *Tuithong* [Tuithang] hao, and so on. Toward the east of Imphal river (Gun in Kuki) were also the tribal villages belonging to the different clans of the Kukis. The mysterious world of the *Kakyen* was later discovered to be a well-populated mountain redoubt of different Kuki clans who lived under their chieftains. *Cheitharol* recorded the first invasion of

Manipur toward the southern mountains in 1790 which again peaked after 1826. We will come back to this point shortly.

Manipur and the Kukis of Southwestern Mountains

We have noted that the southwestern mountains of present Manipur, inhabited by the Kuki tribes, were for centuries under the power of the Tripura kingdom, known in *Rajmala* as Purvakul or “Kuki lands”. We have noted that Manipur’s attention toward the west was drawn by the sporadic invasions of Tripura since the seventeenth century. *Cheitharol* recorded the early invasions of “Takhel” or “Takhen” (Tripura) into the valley of Manipur in 1519 and 1533. Since then, it also recorded the gradual arrival of a few religious individuals from the west, the Mayang (Cachar). Trade and commerce also slowly picked up. The route that passed through the western mountains, then known as *tongcheimarin* (lit. the tunnel through the pipe used in pot smoking), had to be safe and secured for goods, travelers, and merchants.

As the contact between Manipur and Tripura slowly increased, through war and diplomacy, *Cheitharol* also began to notice the presence of the Kuki tribes in the southwestern hills. In 1603, for instance, Manipur had to send its army against the Ranglong Kuki tribe of the Tripura kingdom who then lived on the present Thanlon-Songsang ranges. *Cheitharol* mentions that the Manipur army was “victorious over Langlong in Takhen and captured in battle Aarai Champra and Lintenpa”. (Ibid.: 66). Langlong [Ranglong] was used as the name of a place as well as the tribe in *Cheitharol*. It was the principal village of one of the Kuki tribes who were eventually known as Ranglong.

In 1634, the invasion of the Tripura army into Manipur valley was repulsed and 200 people were captured. (Ibid.: 80). Since then, the relationship between the two kingdoms has become friendly. Thus, in 1638, a “Meetei Reima Takhemi was married (to the king of Takhen)” (Ibid.: 82). One also witnessed a regular flow of goods, traders, and emissaries between the two kingdoms until 1696. In that year it was recorded that the Manipur army again “left to repel the army of Takhen, who came to attack the land” (Ibid.: 108).

The 1720s was a difficult time for Manipur, facing incessant invasions from the Avas (Burmese) in the east and from the Tripura in the west. A peace treaty was however concluded with Tripura in 1727 only to be broken in 1734 when the Manipur army again invaded Takhen (Tripura). The expedition was against the “Kuki lands” (*Purvakul*) of Tripura, the mountain ranges around Tipaimukh junction, particularly over the Vangai ranges (Mangaitang in *Cheitharol* or Vangaitlang in Kuki), inhabited by different Kuki tribes. This event is significant in some ways for the Kukis of the southwestern mountains.

Mangaitang (Vangaitlang) Expedition, 1734

Cheitharol mentions that in 1734 King Mayampa (Garibniwaz) aka Pamhaiba, at the head of his army, invaded Takhen (Tripura). The chronicle is brief but informative:

11 Monday [of Hiyangkei, Oct/Nov], Ningthem left to attack Takhen. Captured Musuklai of Takhen, who was at Roskon in Langlong. Scattered Langlong. They built a bridge over

the Gwai (river) and crossed the river. They marched right up to the top of the Mangaitang mountain range. They completed building the army camp at Sekchai where the Gwai [Barak], Tuyai [Tuivai] and Wakonok, the three (rivers) converged. They defeated Takhen. Scattered Chainu, Satrachit Tonaran [Satrachiton Naran or Narayan] and others, and also the areas in Takhen where Charai people settled were all made tributaries... They placed a stone at [Tuyai] Yirong... 7 Monday [of Phairen – Jan/Feb] Ningthem returned from his attack on Takhen. They killed one person and took 1,100 people alive as prisoners (Ibid.: 142; Bihari, 2012: 97).

The mountain ranges around Tuyai Yirong (present-day Tipaimukh) were the ancestral home of the Kuki tribes such as Ranglong, Saihrem, Chorei, Sakachep, Biete, Aimol, Chiru, Kom, etc., who were commonly known by other Kuki tribes as “Hmarte” (“northern people” by the Kukis of the south who were known by them as “Simte”) or “Kholhangte” (western people by Kukis of the east who were known by others as “Khochungte” who lived on the Kailam-Henglep ranges). As seen from the account of the Cheitharol, the Kukis who were being attacked in 1734 were the Langlong (Ranglong), Charai (Chorei), and others who inhabited the mountain ranges around the Tipaimukh junction such as on Thanlon-Songsang ranges, the Pherzawl-Parbung ranges, Vangai-Bhuban ranges, and northern mountains of present Mizoram. This region has been part of the “Kuki land” or “Purvakul” of Tripura (Takhen).

The capture of Musuklai (Mangsuhlhah?) of Takhen, probably one of the Kuki commanders (Sardars) of the Tripura army, who was at Roskon (?) in Langlong [Ranglong], was indicative of the defeat of the Tripura army apparently man mostly by the Kuki irregulars. The Changsan clan of the Kukis had the tradition that they were serving the Tripura rulers as soldiers for centuries. Their two famous chiefs Mangtinkhup and Mangsuhlhah had a “very cordial relation” with the king of Manipur whose name was “Khangemba (Garibre) [Khagemba]”. Chief Mangtinkhup had founded his village at “Kanglel [Kanglei] Ninglho [Ingkhol]” from where he shifted later to Kameng Demsin Tilla and then to Kourbutilla where he met another Changsan chief named Mangsuhlhah. (Goswami, 1985: 346).

It is evident that the Manipur expedition of 1734 had ended the suzerain power of the Tripura kingdom over its frontier territory (Purvakul or Kuki lands). It also inaugurated, perhaps for the first time, a friendly relationship between Manipur and the Kuki chieftains of the region. The 1100 war captives were mostly the Kukis who were later settled down in the valley of Manipur (as one sees in the case of some Changsan clans) or along the foothills or along the highways, where one finds them even today.

After the Ranglongs were “scattered”, the Manipur army crossed the Gwai (Barak or Tuiruong in Kuki) river at Tuyai Yirong (Tipaimukh, where three rivers meet – Gwai, Tuyai [Tuivai] and Wakonok). The Manipur army then climbed up the Mangaitang (Vangaitlang) mountain ranges inhabited by the same Kuki tribes. From here, the expeditionary forces marched over to the land of the “Charai [Chorei] people” who were said to be “conquered” and Chainu was “dispersed”. The land of Satrachit Tonaran (Satrachiton Naran/Narayan) or the high priest of the Satrachit (Sakichep?) and “others” were also “conquered” and “were all made tributaries”. The Ningthem (king) then erected a stone at Yirong/Irong (Tuyai/Tuivai Yirong [confluence]) to commemorate his victory and returned with 1100 captives.

The court scribes' rendition like "conquered" or "tributaries" needs to be read with care. At most, it was to glorify the throne to the highest pedestal. At the least, it was a mere courtly lexicon. Translation of the old words in modern terms is also significant. While "conquer" must be naturally followed by rule/administration and "tributary" must be followed by annual payment of tribute to the royal treasury, these were not the case with the Manipur kingdom after their victory. Even as the Manipur army returned to Manipur, the devastated Kuki villages were left alone to rebuild their home and hearths.

In its conception, the Mangaitang expedition of 1734 was a military flying column against the recalcitrant Kuki tribal villages of Tripura's eastern frontier (Purvakul). Its significance, however, lies not in "conquering" the territory but in breaking the centuries-old suzerain power of the Tripura kingdom over its Purvakul ("Kuki lands"). It also secured, besides the Kuki war captives, friendly relations with some of the Kuki chieftains which their oral traditions have suggested. On the ruins of Tripura's Purvakul, and after the withdrawal of the Manipur army, one also witnessed the emergence of some powerful Kuki chiefdoms.

The Rise of "Kuki Rajahs"

On the ruins of Tripura's "Kuki lands" (Purvakul), one witnessed the emergence of at least four Kuki chiefdoms in the eighteenth century. The four chiefdoms were based at Paitung (northern Mizoram), Zopui (over the Senvon-Pherzawl ranges), Phaitong (over the Thanlon ranges), and Khongsai (over the Kailam-Senting ranges). Toward the east of Khongsai Rajah were villages of other Kuki tribes until the Kale-Kabaw valley, independent of Tripura and Manipur, but living under their chieftains. Some of the well-known Kuki chieftains of the eastern hills were based at Saitu (over the Tonglon ranges), Saiton/Seitol and Henglep (over the Thangjing ranges), Chahsat/Chassad (over the Thingbung/Haosapi/Haobi ranges), Lonpi/Mombi (over the Dingpi ranges), and so on. Cheitharol mentions the chiefdoms of Saiton and Chassad in particular. Of the Kuki Rajah of Paitung/Paitoo, Francis Buchanan (1798) has recorded as follows:

These Koongkies [Kukis] or Langa, who occupy so much of the country on this [Khongjai] route, are subject to one prince, who can raise 8000 armed men, and who has given the Rajahs of the Moitay [Meitei] and the Tiperah [Tripura] much trouble, while they were making the road [Khongjai road]. In this, he was assisted by the Rajah of Cashar [Cachar]. The Koongky [Kuki] Rajah lives three days journey south from the new road, at a place named Paitoo [Paitung]. (van Schendel, 1992: 136).

The Paitoo (known as Paitung in Kuki), was the principal village of the Kuki Rajah who belonged to the Chorei clan of the Kuki tribes. Paitung is near the present Zawlnuam in northern Mizoram where the remains of the old settlement can still be seen. It was the capital of their famous chief Pu Lalchongpui. Buchanan was informed by the court priest of Manipur, who accompanied the king in Tripura's capital, that the "Koongkies" (Kukis), in collaboration with the rulers of Cachari kingdom (centred at Khaspur then), had given the Rajahs of Manipur and Tripura "much trouble, while they were making the road". Buchanan noted this "road" which begins from Sylhet and then to Banga, Joinangur, Luckipour, Durmaka, Mon-taw, Lum-pai, Lay-rong-poung, Noong-shai,

Ka-ruay, Beesnapour, Pobaw, Mongcham, and Munnypour [Imphal] (Ibid.: 135-136).

Fig. 5. Extract from the Karte von Assam (Map of Assam), 1834 by Heinrich Berghaus.⁸

(Note: The Territory around Tipaimukh (dotted red) is shown to be part of “Paitu” (Paitung) Kuki Rajah territory, to the north of it was “Kutschung Nagas” (read as Khochung Kukis, the Khongjai of *Cheitharol*), to the east was Kungfui Nagas (read as Kungfui Kukis), to the east of Kungfui Kukis was Kom Nagas (Kom Kukis) and to its north was Kupui Nagas (Kabui Nagas). Toward the east Imphal river are shown Anal Nagas (in lower ranges) and Kubo Haos Nagas (read as Kukis) up to the valley of Kubo (Kabaw, Burma). The “Khongjai route” (blue arrow line) is also clearly visible here, passing through Kutschung (Khochung/Khongjai Kuki) villages, then over the Kabui villages of Leimata river, and then to Manipur (Imphal). Even if the information in the map is obscure and scanty (sometimes inaccurate), it roughly shows the geography of different tribes in the southern mountains before the great explosion of the Kuki population toward the northern mountains took place due to pressure from the further south, the point we will come shortly).

The road in question was known as the “Kookee or Khoongie [Khongjai] route” (Khongjai is a Meitei name for Kukis) in Pemberton’s survey report. In his topographical survey, R.B. Pemberton noted the “Kookee or Khoongie [Khongjai] route” which entered the hills from Cachar plain “at a ghaut on the great western bend [toward Cachar] of the Barak river, below the Kookee or Khoongjee village of Soomueeyol”. It then passed through, Pemberton noted, “the country inhabited by the tribe of that name (Khongjais)”. (Pemberton, 1835: 53). From Buchanan’s report, it is evident that the Kuki Rajahs were opposed to the construction of the road that passed through their territory and villages. To complete the construction of the road, Manipur had to send an expedition against the opposing Kuki chieftains of the “Khongjai hills” in 1786, a point we will revisit shortly.

Toward the east of the Rajah of Paitoo (Paitung) was the Kuki Rajah of Zopui who ruled over the Senvon-Pherzawl ranges. Zopui (above the present Senvon village) was the seat of the legendary Pu Chonlut, who belonged to one of the Kuki tribes popularly known by other Kuki tribes as “Khawhlangte” or “Hmarte”. Toward the east of Zopui

chiefdom was the territory of another Kuki Rajah of Phaitong (known to others as Lamyangte under Pu Mangsum) who ruled over the Phaitong-Thanolon ranges. Toward the northeast of Phaitong chiefdom was the powerful Kuki Rajah of Khongsai (known to other Kukis as “Khochungte” or “Khongjai” in Cheitharol). Pu Munvung was the Rajah of Khongsai and popularly known by his people as “Lhangum lengpa [king]” who ruled over the “seven hills” with its capital at Khongsai (Khongjai in Cheitharol) on the Kailam-Senting ranges.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of 6 Kuki chiefdoms in the southern mountains in the eighteenth century. (Redrawn by the author from Google Earth)

Fig. 7. Merit stones of (1) Pu Chonlut at Zopui, (2) Pu Munvung at Khongsai, (3) Pu Nehlam(?) at Chassad, and (4) Pu Mangsum at Phaitong

The Kuki Rajahs of Paitung, Zopui, and Phaitong continued to survive until the middle of the nineteenth century. The emergence of the Sukte and Sailo Rajahs from the further south eventually reduced them into subjection or dispersed their population, the point we shall come back. However, being at the crossroads of the Khongjai road, connecting Manipur and Tripura, the Khongsai chiefdom could not survive the onslaught of Manipur in 1786. As noted above, their persistent opposition to the construction and use of what came to be known as the “Khongjai route” by the two kingdoms was the primary reason why Manipur had to take a bold step to destroy the Khongsai chiefdom in 1786.

Manipur and the Khongsais: Khongjai Hills Expedition, 1786

Cheitharol mentions, in passing, the attack on Khongjai village in 1742 but nothing was known about them until 1784 when some “Khongjais/Khongchais” were received at the court of Kangla (Manipur). (Parratt, I: 153). Within two years of this visit, in 1786, King Chingthangkhempa (Bhagyachandra) mobilized all the available forces of Manipur and went against the principal Khongjai villages on the “Khongchai hills”. (Parratt, II, 2009: 25-28). Cheitharol recorded the expedition in detail. It mentions that King Chingthangkhempa, at the head of the Manipur army, entered the western hills at Lammatong (Bishenpur), and then proceeded to Chainapung, Leimatak (river), the foothills of Pungnaching mountain, an army camp at Mabudhou, Nungsai village, the valley of Kuchu, Tuikhat (river), Tuipui (river), Nungkai village and then to the Khongjai village.

It is evident that the Khongjai village was the principal target of the expedition. However, from the south of Kuchu valley (where a temporary royal residence was erected), the Manipuri forces had to crop through several Khongjai villages until they reached the Khongjai hills. Thus, when the king was at Kuchu camp (6th of Phairen, Jan/Feb) some Khongjais came in and presented bell metal bossed gong with handles, ivory tusk, and a bason. On the same day, the advanced expeditionary party brought back five heads of the Khongjais killed in the battles around the Kuchu valley (identified as the upper course of the Leimatak river where it meets the Tuipit river).

On the 11th of Phairen, the king and his main forces marched up to the Tuikhat river (identified as Tuila river). The advance party was again sent off from there and on the 13th of Phairen the king marched up to Tuipui river (still known by that name, a river flowing northward and joining Irang river at the southwest of Khoupum valley). On the 14th of Phairen, they reached Nungkai (Lungkai), another Khongjai village that still stood near the present village of Lungsai. On the same day, they marched up to the foothills of Khongjai hills where they set up a base camp at Terapokpi in the Tuipui valley. (Ibid.: 25-26). On the 16th the emissaries from Khongjai village were received at the camp, who requested not to attack their villages.

On the 17th of Phairen (Sunday) the army, however, entered the Khongjai hills and “scattered the Khongchais”. They attacked their villages such as Phunchong Yanlam, Khongchai village, Khongchai Haram, Khongchai Hapham, Khongchai Heemang, and Phunchongyon, one after another. It was during this attack that the famous “bowl” and “yotshabi” (three-legged traditional iron oven of the Khongjais) were captured.⁹ Ningthem (the king) “marched through the centre of the Khongchai village and continue up to Tuyai [Tuivai] Yirok”. He was supervising “the feeling of trees for the boats”

there and had “erected a stone pillar at Tuyai”. On the 22nd of Phairen, “Meetengu Chingthangkhopma performed the spear dance in the centre of the Khongchai village and Oukri was also sung to indicate subjugation”. A stone was also “erected” in the village. (Ibid.: 27). Other Kuki villages which had visited the king and paid presents, and those the king had visited on his return journey, were Simangnung, Phaitan, Kentak, Hao Latyampa, Khongnem, Haimang, etc.

The Kuki tradition has it that the destruction of Khongsai village was an important moment in their history. It ended one of the most powerful Kuki chieftains which they called the “Lhangum lengpa [king]” who ruled over the “land of seven hills”. The Lhangum tradition has it that Khongsai village was originally founded by Munvung Lhangum who had a “cordial relationship” with the Moirang Bipa (king) called “Moivang Puba”. (Goswami, 1985: 348). The Khongsai Rajah (“Lhangum lengpa”) entered into both offensive and defensive treaties with the rulers of Moirang. During the reign of “Lhangum lengpa”, the narrative goes on, there was one big iron pot (bowl) where meats never get dried and the people enjoyed the dishes day and night.¹⁰

They migrated from the Khongsai hills to the “Cachar-side” when its chiefdom, centered at Khongsai, was destroyed. (Ibid.). The Thadou tradition has it that Khongsai village was destroyed by one Chinthang [Chingthangkhopma] and Toijam “who were great warriors”. Khongsai village was particularly famous for its agriculture fields called “Saite Loulen”. After they migrated to Cachar, Khongsai village was occupied by the Thanglhai sub-clan of the Lhouvum clan who renamed it “Khongson”. (Shaw, 1928: 47).

The significance of this military expedition of Manipur was that the powerful Kuki Rajah of the Khongjai hills was eventually defeated and the resistance over the new road (Khongjai route) to Bengal was put to rest as subsequent history shows. Thus, after the defeat of the Khongjais, the “Maharaja sent Tenshubam Dolairoi Hanjaba to construct a road up to Gwai [Barak] and fix a wooden post and Ningthem returned to Nungshai stockade on Tuesday, the 2nd”. (Bihari, 2012: 132). We have already noted the account of Buchanan (1793) who was told by a Manipuri priest that the Kukis had given the Rajas of Manipur and Tripura “much trouble, while they were making the road”. The Khongjai Expedition of 1786, however, ended such opposition and it was a strategic necessity for Manipur to control the Khongjai route for trade and diplomacy with the Bengal world.

The Saiton Hills Expedition, 1790

Coming back toward the southern mountains, Cheitharol noted the Manipur expedition in 1790 for the first time. We have already noted the rise of some Kuki chiefdoms in the southern mountains in the eighteenth century. Of these, Cheitharol mentions the chiefdoms of Chahsat (Chassads, over the Haobi ranges) and Saiton (Seitol, over the Thangjing ranges), in particular.¹¹ In 1789/90, a military expedition was sent against the Kuki rajah of Saiton (Seitol).

The month of Phairen (January/February [of 1790]) began on Monday. 17 Wednesday, Meetengu Chingthangkhopma left to attack Saiton. He halted at Bishnupur for one day... 29 Sunday, they reached the army camp at Cheklapai. 2 Wednesday, all the Hao villages were scattered. Meetengu Chingthangkhopma and others sang Oukari (in the village). Meetengu

Chingthangkhopma returned immediately and arrived at Cheklapai. The four Panas, the guru, and others stayed behind and camped in the centre of the village. 3 Thursday, fighting broke out between (the Meeteis) and the Haos at Hathirupa and the Haos killed Khuraichampa the Hajari, and others, a total of nine people. Nine Haos were also shot down. On the following day as the army was leaving in the night, and this came to be known (by the enemy), as they left behind the cannon made of bell metal and many other weapons, these were lost... 9 Thursday, Ningthem returned after his attack of Saiton. (Parratt, II: 34; see also Bihari, 2012: 137).

Due to the disaster, Cheitharol went on narrating the transportation of 8 persons to Loi villages, and those troops who lost their weapons were “tried and beaten in the market”. (Bihari, 2012: 137).

An interesting aspect of the Saiton hills expedition was that, the following month, Sachiphu (March/April [of 1790]), on 8th Thursday, “two Hajaris and forty-one Mayang soldiers who came (from Mayang [Cachar]) to obtain information of the attack on Saiton arrived”. (Parratt, II: 35). It was not clear why the “Mayangs” (the Cacharis of Khaspur) were interested in the Saiton Expedition. The fact that no further Manipur expedition was carried out toward the southern and south-western mountains after the Saiton expedition suggests that the “Mayang” emissary might have expressed their disappointment over the attack on the Kuki villages.

We have already noted that the rajah of Khongsai had migrated toward the “Cachar-side” after his chiefdom was destroyed by the Manipur army in 1786. The Khongsai rajah established a new village on the lower ranges of the Borail mountain, toward the northeast of the Cachar plain, whose village site is still visible today. The Lhangum tradition has it that, they had entered into an offensive and defensive relationship with the Cachari (Dimasa) rulers of Khaspur and fought their wars. It is possible that the Khongjai rajah of Cachar hills might have insisted the Cachari rulers to intervene on the matter concerning their relatives.

While the intervention might have ended Manipur’s expedition against the Kuki villages, one also observes the growing relationship between Manipur and the Kuki chieftains. Thus, in 1791, two villages, Tumman (Toomal) and Saipum (Shaiboon) were punished with a fine of 16 mithuns for attacking Saiton and presenting 16 heads to the king “as war trophies”. (Parratt, II: 39; Singh, 68). This improving relationship between the Kukis (Khongjais) and Manipur was also evident during this time by the frequent visit of the Kukis to the court of Kangla. Thus, in 1792, the Khongjais were received in the court twice. (Parratt, II: 41-42; Bihari, 141-42). In 1793, the “Haos from Saiton came and paid obeisance to Ningthem”. (Parratt, II: 42; Bihari, 142).

To what extent such a relationship was conceived is not very clear from Cheitharol. Yet, during the Burmese invasions and occupation of Manipur (known in Manipur history as the “seven-year devastation”), one can observe that some Meitei princes and their followers took shelter in the hills among the Kukis. William Shaw recorded the oral account of the Kukis as:

At the time of the Burmese Invasion the Raja of Manipur fled for protection to the house of Khongsat Kuki’s father where he ate ga (beans) only for several months. When the Burmese left the Valley he returned home with Khongsat’s father and Kaikhohal Kuki. So, the Manipuris have always treated the Kukis with respect since then (Shaw, 1928: 48).

It was said that about 300-400 Kuki warriors took part in the *Tuku* (guerrilla) army of Prince Herachandra (“Tuku Ningthou”) who fought against the occupying Burmese army. *Cheitharol* stated that during the Burmese occupation of Imphal valley, “Ibungshi Herachandra came down from Khongsai village and collected Meitei Chakyelpas and organised *Tuku* (Ruffian) on Friday, the 3rd of the month of *Lamda*” (Bihari, 170).

Manipur-Kuki Relations Post-Yandaboo

The occupying Burmese army was expelled from Manipur during the First Anglo-Burmese War and a peace treaty was concluded at Yandaboo in 1826. Maharaja Gambhir Singh was put up on the throne of Manipur with British support. A 2000-strong Manipur army was also equipped by the British for the defense of the Manipur kingdom. The British government of India wanted to see a powerful Manipur as a buffer state against the threat of Burmese invasion. With the British Empire backing behind, the Maharaja immediately started a whirlwind military campaign over the mountains, surrounding the valley of Manipur.¹² Until his death in 1834, Maj. W. McCulloch remarked: “he [Gambhir Singh] was employed in coercing the hill tribes and in bringing down from them the fugitives who had taken refuge amongst them from Burmese oppression”. (McCulloch, 1859: 9).

This policy of “coercion” was purposed to keep the hill tribes under control and to make Manipur a powerful border kingdom. This, being the British frontier project, was a strategy to prevent the Burmese from interfering again in the affairs of Northeast India and Bengal. However, such coercive actions only generated defiant resistance from the hill tribes, particularly from the southern mountains. *Cheitharol* recorded a series of military campaigns under Senapati Nara Singh in the southern mountains, who had, through war and diplomacy, eventually developed a cordial relationship with the Kuki chieftains.

While the Kukis of the southern mountains were struggling and navigating against the invasions from the north, the appearance of two powerful Kuki tribes from further south (the Sakte-Kamhaus from the Chin Hills and the Sailo-Lusheis from the Lushai Hills) in about the 1840s make things even more precarious and distressing for the Khongjais. Like Manipur, the two powerful tribes also took to a policy of coercion and expansion, and very soon were successful in invading the southern valley of Manipur which the latter had to respond without much success. Caught up in between the devil and the deep blue sea, the Kukis (Khongjais) of the southern mountains responded in at least four different ways. (Guite, 2011).

First, they fought against the invaders with the hope that they would be able to protect their lands from being ravaged. They were initially successful but as the incessant attacks and pressure from both the north and the south were insurmountable they took three different courses. First, some of them, instead of submitting to either of the two powers (from the north and the south) chose to migrate toward the northern mountains where they founded new settlements there with or without the consent of the Naga tribes. To the extent that they fought for land against the native inhabitants there, the Kukis have become, to the British authority, an “administrative nuisance”. To the extent that they were given lands by some native villages in lieu of protection from their

powerful neighbours, the Kukis have been welcomed as “kajol” (my friend) and peace-broker. Second, some of them have also submitted to the Rajahs of Suktes and Lusheis, paid tributes, and remained in the southern mountains or migrated further south in the lands of their overlords as their subjects. Third, a certain number of villages also took shelter under the protection of Manipur and the British authority of Cachar. They entered into a friendly agreement with them, and equipped with their firearms, protected the frontier against raids from the further south. Thus, in 1859, some Kuki chieftains from the southern mountains entered into a friendly agreement with the Maharajah of Manipur at Moirang. The treaty at Moirang was recorded in Cheitharol as:

The first day of Kalen (May [1859]) was Tuesday. On Monday the 7th, the Maharaja went to Moirang to make friendship with the Khongjais. On Tuesday the 8th, the Khongjais took oath before the Maharaja that they would guard him against the Akam-Haos [Kamhaus] and requested for supply of arms and equipments. 200 muskets were given to them after they had promised and drank the water offered to 9 Sylvan deities and some portion of the water was sprinkled on the musket, sword, spear and weapons for protection from Akam-Haos. On Saturday the 9th, the Maharaja returned to the Palace (Bihari, 249-50).

After this, a line of Kuki villages was established along the foothills of the southern valley, nicknamed “sepyo villages”. They were given firearms to protect the frontier from raids and to act as “scouts” against the movements of the Suktes and the Lusheis. In his “memorandum” to the Government of India, dated 18 July 1861, McCulloch wrote:

Beyond the Manipur boundary are the Soote [Sukte] and Loosai [Lushai] tribes. These are both powerful and dangerous. . . . In connection with these people, and as a protection to the south of the valley, the Rajah and I have established in the south villages of Kookies, to whom are given arms, and whom we call sepyo villages. They are to be unrestricted in their cultivation, and have to send scouts to watch the tribes at the season when they are most able to move about and do mischief. (Mackenzie, 1884: 157).

A similar policy was also adopted by the British authority of Cachar. Since their occupation of Cachar in 1832, the British officers reported the Kuki tribes to the eastern and southern hills of Cachar plain who “have been gradually driving one another in a northerly direction”. Many of them took their settlements (known as “Kookie punjies”) along the borders of the Cachar district, in the lower ranges and uninhabited spurs, under the protection of Cachar authority. (Ibid.: 287). A 200-strong “Kuki Levy” was also formed in 1850 to protect the plains from Lushei raids. From the Cachar district, a good number of the Kuki population were also later transplanted into a line of villages called “Kuki colony” on the Borail ranges by the British. They were given arms and engaged in protecting the inhabitants of the North Cachar Hills and north-western hills of Manipur from the powerful Angami raids.

It was under such distressing political circumstances that the Kukis of the southern mountains of Manipur and Cachar were eventually forced to take a flight from their native hills to the northern mountains of Manipur, North Cachar, and Naga Hills. The displacement and dispersal of their population during this time, with or without the support of the colonial state, was so significant that they even got the name “migratory

tribes” and “bird of passage”. Yet, they were not migratory in their native hills is attested in all the earlier accounts. McCulloch, for instance, noted: “Originally they were not migratory, but have assumed this character latterly”. (McCulloch, 1859: 58).¹³

The “Kuki Levy” of Manipur Army

Since the Moirang treaty, we can see that a good number of Kuki chieftains remain friendly with the rulers of Manipur. Since then, it is evident that the Kuki irregulars have always formed part of the Manipur army and fought its wars. James Johnstone (1879) reported that in addition to the regular troops of Manipur state, “some 700 Kuki irregulars are kept up” always by the Maharaja and they “are naturally more courageous and better soldiers than the Manipuris”.¹⁴ Their constant presence inside the Kangla palace was evident during the Anglo-Manipur War, 1891. Testimonies of a few individuals show that the Kukis had been fighting against the British troops inside the palace on the night of 24 March 1891 when the rising began.

The deposed Raja Surchandra, for instance, reported to the media at Calcutta that “the Rajah will not kill Mr. Quinton or other captives” but “the Kuki hillmen are uncontrollable. They might rush and kill the captives. The Kukis number 10,000 warriors who invariably killed the prisoners”.¹⁵ The *Times* Rangoon correspondent reported that, “After Mr. Quinton’s capture, he and the two British Officers and the bugler were taken before the Regent, who ordered them to be made over to the Kuki Levies to be killed”.¹⁶

The participation of the Kukis and Nagas in the war was later confirmed by Senapati Tikendrajit who had informed the matter to one British Signaller C. Williams. Before setting out to the British territory after his release from Manipur jail, Williams was told by the Senapati that “he is quite innocent of the murder [of British officers on the night of 24 March], he did not order them, and all rest that has been done was done by his sepoy, who were most uncontrollable just then, and the Nagas and Kukis did all the mischief”.¹⁷

Maj. Grant who once served as the Captain of Manipur Levy, and who led the British forces from Burma against the Manipur army during the war, reported that “the army” of Manipur in the war “numbered 5,000 Manipuris armed with smooth-bores, and 1,000 or 1,200 Kuki irregulars with flint muskets”.¹⁸ While their participation in the Anglo-Manipur War was evident from diverse sources, it was probable that they bolted later from the field when the war went against Manipur. William Shaw recorded that “most of the Thadous fought for the Raja on that occasion” but later left when “they knew that the latter [Manipuris] had no chance”. (Shaw, 1928: 49).

While visiting Losao village in 1892, Bertram Carey noted that “many of the inhabitants speak Manipuri” and he was told that “many were present at the massacre of the British officers in Manipur in 1891”. (Carey, II, 1886: cxxv). He reported: “the Nwites [Guites] of Sumkam’s village [Tonglon] and Losao admit that they took part in the fight at the Residency, but they returned immediately afterwards to their homes, and then contented themselves with spreading the report that thousands of our people [British] had been killed in Manipur”. (Carey, I, 1886: 55). The Kuki irregulars were also credited with pursuing the withdrawing British forces as well as obstructing the reinforcements in the hills. It was reported:

...several Ghoorkhas have been retaken prisoner by the Kukis and one European has escaped. The Kukis are troublesome on the road from Cachar to Manipur, making raids. Fears are entertained of a rising among the Hillmen in the district [Manipur].¹⁹

Maj. Grant column from Burma was harassed all along the hills and confronted at Tegnoupal village by the Kuki irregulars. Thus, when the war goes against Manipur, William Shaw recorded, the “Sena Koireng [Tikendrajit] fled to Tonglhu Chief of Chahsat [now in the eastern hills] and sought his protection” but Tonglhu “could not grant such protection” against the mighty British army (Shaw, 1928: 49).

For such admirable feats in the formation of the modern Manipur state, the Kukis got the name “pan ngakpa” (keeper of the [hill] fortress) in Manipur history. The close association of the Kuki chieftains with the rulers of Manipur, in their wars and diplomacy, was one primary factor why the British’s Manipur-Chin boundary commission (1894) had awarded the southern mountains, the ancestral home of the Kukis, to Manipur. It was protested by the Chin Hills authority for being a part of the Kamhau’s domain but for reasons that large numbers of the Khongjai (Kuki) population had been already settled down within the Manipur boundary (based on 1859 treaty), and the Kukis being already associated with the state formation of modern Manipur, the recommendation of the boundary commission was finally accepted by the government of India.

Fig. 5. The Southern Boundary of Manipur (1) before (imaginary line) 1894 and (2) after 1894. Sources: Johnstone, *My Experiences in Manipur and Naga Hills*, p. 35; <https://www.mapsofindia.com/maps/manipur/>

The disbandment of the Manipur army in 1892, after the Anglo-Manipur War, was strongly felt by the Kukis. The degradation of their status from being a martial tribe of the state to coolies and revenue-paying subjects under the British administration since 1892 hugely eroded their loyalty to the state. Hence, in collusion with some Meitei revolutionaries, led by Chingakhamba Sanachaoba, the Kukis had fought against the British government during the First World War. It was popularly known in Manipur history as the “Kuki Rebellion” or the “Anglo-Kuki War” (1917-1919). (Guite & Haokip,

2018). It was a war attempted to expel the British colonial Raj from Manipur and to restore the old system where the Kukis had enjoyed their freedom and held a respectable status in the state. The failure of the rising was deeply regretted, but William Shaw later found them that, “Their tails are not down and I have heard it said that they hope to become a ‘Raj’ some day”. (Shaw, 1928: 23). The “Raj” came in 1947 but the ongoing conflicts in the state since India's independence seem to indicate that the people of the state are not yet contented.

Conclusion

A brief navigation of the objective history of the Kukis in Northeast India shows that they, along with their kinsmen TBF, have been continuously living in the region since ancient times. Linguistic and genetic studies suggest their presence in the region since the 2nd millennium BCE. Hindu myths and mythologies suggest their existence since the time of the Mahabharata. Buddhist literary sources suggested their existence in eastern India since Emperor Asoka's time (the 3rd Cent. BCE). From archaeological sources, it is evident that they have been in the region as a well-settled agriculturist in ancient Tripura (advance-guard of the TBF's long march toward the tropics) since the 7th Cent. CE. The megalithic remains of their tradition also similarly suggested that they were a well-settled hill community on the eastern mountains by the 7th century CE, possibly the high noon of their civilization. Their continuous existence in the region during the medieval period is also attested by the royal court chronicles of Tripura, Manipur, and Burma, besides a few inscriptions.

No wonder, historians generally held that Kukis are, and for that matter the TBF, one of the earliest inhabitants of the region. Gangmumei Kabui, for instance, stated that Kukis are one of the earliest inhabitants of Manipur whose settlement dates back to the pre-historic time “along with or after the Meitei advent in Manipur valley”. (Kabui, 1991: 24). R.C. Majumdar and N. Bhattasali's *History of India* (1930: 6-7), said that Kukis are one of the prehistoric tribes of India and their settlement in India preceded the Dravidians who now live in south India. R.P. Singh's “Kukis” in Danver's *Native Peoples of the World*, (2015: 543-44) wrote: “The history of the Mongoloid ancestors of the Kukis dates back to 500 B.C.E in India. Archaeologists believe that some Kuki groups migrated to the Manipur Hills of northeastern India in prehistoric times... Some historians believe that the Kukis are related to the Tiladai people... Others believe that the Kukis were the earliest people who inhabited India”.

Endnotes

1. Bhattacharjee felt that the Kukis who had already adopted paddy cultivation by this time could have been already absorbed within the plain society is most probable. They represent the advanced guard of TBF (and the Kukis) migration toward the tropics. It is possible that they could also have re-ethnicized themselves in the hills when population/political pressure in the plains of Bengal was mounting which was the case in many places. (See, Scott, 2009).

2. A shrine was installed later by the rulers of the Cachari kingdom in the 17th Cent. Since then, Bhuban caves have become the annual pilgrimage centre for lakhs of

Hindu devotees.

3. This idea is strongly shared among the Hmar tribes who also believe that a river island at the confluence of Barak (Tuiruong) and Tuivai is another gateway. The Lusheis talked about Rihdil Lake. The Thadou-Kuki called the gateway as Lhanpelkot (dead man's gateway) and Thijonbung (the range where dead people's souls march). They still believed that the soul of the dead marched toward the west and hence usually placed the head of the dead body toward the west, possibly pointing toward the Bhuban caves, a gateway to mithikho (dead man village). Mithikho is believed to be under the earth, the subterranean region, where all their ancestors live. Thus, whenever there is an earthquake, they shout in a loud voice "Kadam naove, Manmasi chate kadam naove" (We are fine; the children of Manmasi are fine). They believed that earthquakes are caused by their ancestors or a visitation of their ancestors who would like to know whether they are doing well.

4. Later evidences suggested that the term "Langla" or "Langa" is another name for "Kuki". (van Schendel, 1992: 136).

5. Their works seem so influential that even academic historians would take their argument forward without offering any critique.

6. Rev. Long also noted that Thanangchi (Thanansi) was the former capital of Tripura which the Marauding expeditions of the Kukis caused it to be removed to some secure place.

7. In 1614, for instance, it mentions that "The sovereign king from the land of Kyang riding a white horse fought with the sword at Samsok". (Parratt, I: 73-74).

8. See, <https://www.raremaps.com/gallery/detail/46251/karte-von-assam-und-seinen-nachbar-landern-gest-v-w-bros-berghaus>

9. This bowl has been a legend in the family history of the Lhangum clan. They still talk about this whenever they narrate the history of Lhangumlengpa (king). The bowl was said to be never emptied with meat, and always on the fire.

10. Interview with Pu Chungsat Khongsai, pipa of the Lhangum clan, dated 13 March 2021 at his residence in Langol Housing Complex, Imphal.

11. Saiton (Seitol) was a Kuki village of the Haokip clan. Its original village site was on the Thangjing (Thangting) ranges where the expedition of 1790 took place. From this original site, they migrated to the present Saiton village (near Kumbi/Torbung) in the plain in 1858.

12. For details of his military campaigns, see, the Cheitharol from 1826 to 1834.

13. Today, one finds them scattered in almost all the states of the Northeast region – Mizoram, Manipur, Tripura, Nagaland, Assam and Meghalaya.

14. National Archives of India (NAI), Lieut. Col. J. Johnstone, Political Agent, Manipur, in temporary charge, Naga Hills, to Secy., Chief Commissioner of Assam, 2nd November 1879.

15. "The Manipur Disaster: Account of the attack", *The Daily Free Press*, Friday, April 3, 1891, Image from the British Library, London.

16. "The Manipur Massacre", *Poverty Bay Herald*, Vol. xviii, Issue 6076, 27 May 1891, p. 4; "The Manipur Rising", *Pahiatua Star and Eketahuna Advertiser*, Vol. 5, Issue 498, 26 May 1891, p. 2; "The Manipur Massacre", *Hawke's Bay Herald*, vol. xxvi, Issue 8979, 23 May 1891, p. 4.

17. Manipur State Archives, Imphal: R-1/5-C, 215: 'British correspondence (1891) relating to Manipur: Signaller C. Williams to the Director-General of Telegraphs: 'Experiences of Signaller C. Williams, in charge of Chief Commissioner's Telegraph Camp, Manipur'.
18. *The Tablet*, Saturday, April 11, 1891, London, England, p. 6-7. "The Manipur Disaster: Account of the attack", *The Daily Free Press*, Friday, April 3, 1891, Image the British Library London.

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Interview

Interview with Pu Chungsat Khongsai, pipa of the Lhangum clan, dated 13 March 2021 at his residence in Langol Housing Complex, Imphal.